

SITE <u>GS</u> SPHINX	DATE 6/25/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.575 to 10.615	Bottom: 10.49
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 14 top cm		Width:	Length:	Depth: 9-115

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions		
①	GYPSUM-SAND MOTTLED	Grey-white	Soft (Gypsum) BUT Packed (hard)	Fine	T	○	Lm	Gp ✓
							Gr	Char
							Do	
					D		Ba	
							Al	
							Other	
②	GYSUM	OFF white to yellowish	Very COMPACT	Rough Grainy	T	○	Lm ✓ Frags small	Gp
							Gr	Char ✓ FLECKS
							Do	
					D		Ba	
							Al	Insect Remains
							Other	Soft yellow stone like sand stone
③	SAND "Granite Dust"				T	○	Lm ✓	Gp
							Gr ✓ Crushed	Char <small>Some Fine Flecks Few</small>
							Do ✓ Pelerite	
					D		Ba ✓	Mud Spot (1)
							Al	
							Other	Insect Remains
④	SAND	TAN-YELLOW	SOFT	Fine	T	○	Lm	Gp
							Gr	Char
							Do	
					D		Ba	1 Mud Spot
							Al	
							Other	
⑤	Gypsum	OFF White-Buff	Hard Compact	Fine Powder-like when dry	T	○	Lm	Gp
							Gr	Char Fine specks
							Do	
					D		Ba	
							Al	
							Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 1	No./ 29 30 31 32	B&W: Roll/ 1	No./ 24-27
DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20	Feature Plan:	Sections: Two sections w. Fill	

REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: ① Perhaps associated w/ nearby SL cable line.
 ② Lit. disintegrated granite - 1cm dia. chips to very small grains - also dolerite and/or basalt
 Does ⑤ indicate hole originally gypsum filled (or packing for post?), then cleared and refilled w/ ②-③. Finally paved over w/ ②? (OVER)

Insect Remains - some kind of Bee? Dried bodies fuzzy - stripped. Also "bags" - larvae?

Limestone bottom of FHS reddened - rust colored. Scorched?

30

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